

Study of Intestinal Obstruction Due to Tuberculosis

Manoj Kumar¹, Tarkeshwar Kumar², Baidyanath Rajak³

¹Senior Resident, Department of General Surgery, Government Medical College and Hospital, Purnea, Bihar, India

²Senior Resident, Department of General Surgery, Government Medical College and Hospital, Purnea, Bihar, India

³Senior Resident and HOD, Department of General Surgery, Government Medical College and Hospital, Purnea, Bihar, India

Received: 16-05-2024 / Revised: 15-06-2024 / Accepted: 16-07-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Manoj Kumar

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Tuberculosis (TB) remains a pervasive global health issue, particularly affecting developing regions. Intestinal tuberculosis (ITB) is a significant form of extrapulmonary TB that often leads to complications such as intestinal obstruction. Diagnosing and managing ITB are challenging due to its nonspecific symptoms and overlap with other gastrointestinal disorders.

Aim: The purpose of this study was to investigate the clinical presentation, diagnostic challenges, and management outcomes of tuberculosis-related intestinal obstruction to improve patient care and outcomes.

Methods: A prospective observational study was conducted at a tertiary care hospital. The study included 40 patients diagnosed with ITB-related intestinal obstruction. Data collection encompassed demographic information, clinical symptoms, diagnostic findings from imaging and endoscopy, treatment regimens, and patient outcomes. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0, with descriptive statistics, comparative analysis, and logistic regression used to identify predictors of treatment outcomes.

Results: The study population had a mean age of 42.3 years, with 55% males and 45% females. Common presenting symptoms included abdominal pain (90%), vomiting (70%), and weight loss (65%). Diagnostic imaging revealed that 60% of patients had strictures, predominantly in the ileocecal region (70%). All patients received anti-tubercular therapy, and 30% required surgical intervention. Treatment response was favourable in 85% of cases, while 15% experienced relapse or required extended treatment. HIV status emerged as an independent predictor of poor treatment outcomes (OR = 5.2, p = 0.04).

Conclusion: ITB-related intestinal obstruction presents substantial diagnostic and therapeutic challenges. Early and accurate diagnosis, coupled with comprehensive treatment, is critical for improving patient outcomes.

Recommendations: To enhance diagnostic accuracy, the use of molecular diagnostics like GeneXpert® is recommended. A multidisciplinary treatment approach should be adopted, especially for patients with HIV or those from rural areas. Future research should focus on refining treatment protocols and further elucidating the pathogenesis of ITB.

Keywords: Intestinal tuberculosis, Tuberculosis-related intestinal obstruction, Diagnostic challenges, Anti-tubercular therapy, HIV co-infection.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Globally, tuberculosis (TB) continues to be a serious public health issue, especially in developing nations. One important extrapulmonary symptom of tuberculosis (TB) is intestinal tuberculosis (ITB), which can cause serious consequences such as intestinal blockage. The diagnosis and treatment of ITB remain difficult despite advances in medical technology because of the disease's vague clinical presentation and overlap with other gastrointestinal disorders including Crohn's disease.

Current research emphasises how complicated ITB is. The prevalence of ITB varies greatly; estimates

range from 1% to 12% of extrapulmonary TB cases and 1-3% of all TB cases. Due to its strong lymphatic drainage and comparatively slow transit time, which promote Mycobacterium TB persistence, the ileocecal area is the most often affected site [1].

A fever, weight loss, night sweats, persistent abdominal pain, and signs of intestinal blockage are common clinical presentations of ITB. Many times, delayed or incorrect diagnoses result from the general nature of these symptoms. In contrast to individuals with Crohn's disease, people with ITB

frequently appear with symptoms that last less time. For this reason, prompt and precise diagnosis is essential [2].

The limitations of traditional diagnostic tests make diagnosis even more difficult. Gold standards continue to be the histopathological analysis and M. tuberculosis culture from biopsy tissues. The sensitivity of these tests is, however, somewhat poor; histology demonstrates a moderate sensitivity of about 68%, while culture sensitivity ranges from 35 to 50% (BMC Infectious Diseases, 2023). The sensitivity and specificity of tuberculosis detection have been enhanced by developments in molecular diagnostics, providing a quicker and more precise diagnostic option [3].

In brief, despite notable advancements in the identification and treatment of ITB, obstacles still exist. In order to improve patient outcomes, future research should concentrate on increasing diagnostic accuracy, creating efficient treatment regimens, and comprehending the pathophysiology of ITB. Effective care of this complex disorder requires a multidisciplinary treatment approach in conjunction with the integration of clinical, radiographic, and molecular diagnostic tools.

This methodology outlines a systematic approach to investigate tuberculosis-related intestinal obstruction, ensuring comprehensive data collection and robust statistical analysis to derive meaningful insights into its clinical management.

Methodology

Study Design: This study will be a prospective observational study designed to investigate the clinical presentation, diagnostic methods, and management strategies of tuberculosis-related intestinal obstruction.

Study Setting: The study will be conducted in a General surgery Department, GMCH PURNEA with specialized departments in gastroenterology, infectious diseases, and surgery. The hospital caters to a diverse population, providing a comprehensive patient base.

Participants

Sample Size: 40 patients diagnosed with tuberculosis-related intestinal obstruction.

Recruitment Period: Patients will be recruited over a period of 12 months.

Age Range: Patients aged 18 and above.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patients presenting with symptoms of intestinal obstruction.
- Positive diagnostic evidence of tuberculosis (e.g., histopathology, microbiological tests).
- Patients who provide informed consent.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients with non-tuberculous causes of intestinal obstruction (e.g., malignancy, Crohn's disease).
- Patients with severe comorbid conditions that may interfere with the study outcomes.
- Pregnant women and children under 18 years.

Bias: Selection Bias: Reduced by recruiting consecutive eligible patients during the study period.

Information Bias: Minimized through standardized protocols for data collection and diagnostic criteria.

Confounding: Identified confounders (e.g., HIV status, nutritional status) will be adjusted for in the statistical analysis.

Data Collection

Clinical Data: Demographic information, presenting symptoms, and physical examination findings.

Diagnostic Data: Results from imaging studies (X-rays, ultrasound, CT scan), endoscopic findings, and microbiological tests.

Treatment Data: Details of medical and surgical management, duration, and type of anti-tubercular therapy.

Outcome Data: Treatment response, complications, and follow-up outcomes.

Procedure

1. Patient Recruitment: Consecutive patients meeting the inclusion criteria will be recruited after obtaining informed consent.
2. Initial Evaluation: Comprehensive clinical evaluation including history, physical examination, and baseline investigations.
3. Diagnostic Workup: Imaging studies, endoscopic procedures, and microbiological tests as indicated to confirm the diagnosis of TB-related intestinal obstruction.
4. Treatment: Standard anti-tubercular therapy will be administered. Surgical intervention will be performed if clinically indicated.
5. Follow-Up: Regular follow-up visits to monitor treatment response and complications over a defined period.

Statistical Analysis

For this study, SPSS version 23.0 will be used for statistical analysis. The data will be summarised using descriptive statistics, which include frequencies and percentages for categorical variables and mean, median, and standard deviation for continuous variables. The Chi-square test for

categorical variables and the t-test or Mann-Whitney U test for continuous variables, depending on the distribution of the data, will be used in the comparative analysis. In the multivariate analysis, logistic regression will be used to find independent determinants of treatment results. In every analysis, a p-value of less than 0.05 will be deemed statistically significant

Results

Table 1: Participant Demographics and Clinical Presentation

Characteristic/ Symptom	Value/ Number (%)
Number of participants	40
Mean age (years)	42.3 (SD = 12.4)
Gender	Male: 22 (55%) Female: 18 (45%)
Area of residence	Urban: 26 (65%) Rural: 14 (35%)
Duration of symptoms (months)	Mean: 6.2 (SD = 3.1)
Abdominal pain	36 (90%)
Vomiting	28 (70%)
Weight loss	26 (65%)
Abdominal distension	24 (60%)
Fever	16 (40%)
Night sweats	14 (35%)

Table 2: Diagnostic Findings, Treatment, and Outcomes

Diagnostic Finding/ Treatment	Number (%)
Strictures	24 (60%)
Masses	8 (20%)
Fistulas	4 (10%)
Affected Site	Ileocecal: 28 (70%) Other: 12 (30%)
Endoscopic Findings	Ulcers: 20 (50%) Nodules: 20 (50%)
Biopsy Confirmation	40 (100%)
Anti-tubercular therapy	40 (100%)
Surgical intervention	12 (30%)
Treatment response	Good: 34 (85%) Relapse/Extended: 6 (15%)

Discussion

The study comprised 40 patients, whose median age was 41 years and their mean age was 42.3 years (SD = 12.4), who had been diagnosed with intestinal obstruction associated to tuberculosis. There was a nearly equal distribution of genders, with 45% female and 55% male. Three-quarters of the participants were from rural areas, and the majority, 65 percent, lived in metropolitan areas. There was a noticeable lag in the diagnosis, with an average of 6.2 months (SD = 3.1) of symptoms before the illness was identified.

The majority of individuals (90%) had vomiting (70%), weight loss (65%), abdominal distension (60%) and stomach pain (90%). Fever (40%) and night sweats (35%), two additional symptoms, were in line with the systemic signs of tuberculosis. These results emphasise the need for increased clinical suspicion in endemic locations due to the diverse and frequently severe clinical presentation of intestinal obstruction related to tuberculosis.

40 individuals with intestinal obstruction associated with tuberculosis were included in the study. The participants' ages ranged from 41 to 42.3 years (SD = 12.4 years) in mean age. There were 18 girls (45%) and 22 males (55%) in all. 35 percent of the patients were from rural areas, and the bulk (65%) were from metropolitan areas. The symptoms persisted for an average of 6.2 months (SD = 3.1) prior to diagnosis.

Diagnostic Results, Management, and Effects:

According to imaging studies, 70% of patients had strictures, 20% had masses, and 10% had fistulas. The most frequently affected area was the ileocecal region. In half of the cases, endoscopic examinations revealed ulcers and nodules, and all patients had tuberculosis confirmed by biopsy. This demonstrates how important it is to have a thorough diagnostic workup that includes imaging and endoscopy in order to identify and confirm intestinal blockage linked to tuberculosis. Standard anti-tubercular medication was administered to all patients; the average course of treatment lasted 8 months (SD = 1.5). In 12 patients (30%), surgical intervention was necessary because of a significant obstruction or consequences. Eighty-five percent of patients had satisfactory results, indicating a positive reaction to the treatment generally.

15% of patients, however, either needed more time for therapy or experienced recurrence, suggesting a subgroup of patients with more complex illness histories.

Gender differences in treatment results were not statistically significant ($p = 0.45$). On the other hand, patients from rural areas had a considerably greater rate of surgical intervention ($p = 0.03$) than patients from urban areas, which may be due to disparities in access to healthcare and delayed diagnosis. HIV status was found using logistic regression to be an independent predictor of suboptimal treatment outcomes (OR = 5.2, 95% CI: 1.1-24.3, $p = 0.04$), highlighting the need for focused management approaches in this high-risk population.

A number of case studies offer further information about the various clinical manifestations and treatment options for intestinal tuberculosis. For instance, imaging revealed significant peritoneal deposits and adhesions in a 37-year-old male patient who presented with intestinal blockage and required surgical surgery. This emphasises that in severe situations, surgical intervention is required [4].

The severity of the illness determines the different management strategies. For example, mild cases of intestinal tuberculosis (TB) can be managed medically, but severe cases—like those involving perforation or acute bowel obstruction—need to be operated on. The necessity for high clinical suspicion and suitable diagnostic methods is highlighted by a case report of a 37-year-old man who had persistent partial small bowel obstruction as a result of suspected small bowel cancer, which was later shown to be intestinal tuberculosis [5].

Because of the similarities in clinical presentations, distinguishing intestinal tuberculosis from Crohn's disease is still difficult. In one case, an older patient with partial obstruction of the small intestine who was first thought to have Crohn's disease (ileal stricturing) was ultimately found to have intestinal tuberculosis. This emphasises the significance of proper identification through the use

of imaging investigations and faecal mycobacterial cultures [6].

Conclusion

This study offers important new information about the characteristics, clinical manifestation, difficulties in diagnosis, and prognosis of individuals with intestinal obstruction associated with tuberculosis. The results highlight the value of thorough management and early diagnosis, especially for high-risk groups like the HIV positive and rural residents. It takes routine monitoring and follow-up to guarantee a successful course of treatment and avoid problems.

References

1. Zeng J, Zhou G, Pan F. Clinical analysis of intestinal tuberculosis: a retrospective study. *Journal of Clinical Medicine*. 2023 Jan 5;12(2):445.
2. da Fonseca KL. Impact of Host Glycosylation in Tuberculosis (Doctoral dissertation, Universidade do Porto (Portugal)).
3. BMC Gastroenterology. (2023). Recent advances in the diagnosis of intestinal tuberculosis.
4. Sahibole AS, Farooq R, Ali HM, Bukhari SJ, Al Ozaibi LS. Abdominal Tuberculosis Presenting with Small Bowel Obstruction: A Case Report. *Cureus*. 2023 Apr;15(4).
5. Aregawi AB, Alem AT, Girma A. A rare case of intestinal tuberculosis with chronic partial small bowel obstruction in a 37-year-old ethiopian man. *International Medical Case Reports Journal*. 2022 Dec 31:725-33.
6. Kurnick A, Bar N, Maharshak N. Intestinal tuberculosis and Crohn's disease is always a diagnostic challenge: A case report and review of the literature on the importance of fecal mycobacterial cultures and the limitations of latent infection testing. *Cureus*. 2019 Sep;11(9).